

“Developed nation and its characteristics”

Development model towards Viksit Bharat 2047

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Abstract—As we are aware, across the world around one-third are developed nations, and others are struggling to achieve that goal as it is a desire for all the nations, and is the ultimate goal of all the states to achieve the tag of the developed nation, all countries have their strategies for growth and development and they follow that particular model to achieve the goal of a developed nation. So as we are talking about developed nations we will discuss their characteristics in detail and also will understand one of the models for achieving the goal of a developed nation.

Keywords—Economics, developed nation, economic model, strategy for growth and development, characteristics of developed nation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Develop Nations in reference to sociology, economic, and political terms, denote countries characterized by robust economic performance, high living standards, and advanced institutional framework. we have to remember that developed nations are typically distinguished by high GDP per capita, well-developed infrastructures, and sophisticated governing systems ensuring political stability and social welfare. This paper aspires to provide a comprehensive analysis of characteristics that define development and explain the welfare model for development.

II. METHODOLOGY:-

In this paper qualitative approach is used, based on a literature review analysis of secondary data (content analysis) from reputed international organization reports.

- Document analysis: summarizing the reports of the World Bank, OECD, UNDP, and academic journals.
- theoretical framework:- creating development theory by contextualizing the observed characteristics.

III. DISCUSSION:-

In recent eras, economists have argued that development is not development without environmental sustainability and social equity. Further debate has shifted from a unidimensional approach which majorly emphasizes economic output to a multi-dimensional approach covering human development, ecological stability, and quality of governance. These changes explain that long-term prosperity must balance economic growth with social and environmental considerations.

IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPED NATION:

Enhanced living standard:-

high living standard found in developed Nations, having access to elevated health, and education services, high life expectancy, and low child mortality rate. in such countries per-capita income is also high and the optimum tax structure, benefits from greater disposable income for consumption and recreational activities.

Advanced infrastructure:-

development Nation has a well-developed infrastructure per head covering better connectivity, communication facilities, energy supply, and major regions in the country equipped with basic amenities like sanitation, waste management, water supply, health care, education et cetera.

Strong and diverse economy:-

as we know the diversified economy, a mixture of primary (agriculture), secondary (manufacturing), tertiary (service), and technology is characteristic of the developed country. Developed nations do not rely on only a particular sector and have stable and effective banking, capital markets, and financial markets.

Technological Innovation:-

further developed Nations achieved expertise in advanced technology and innovation they emphasized research and development (R&D) more likely areas of AI, biotechnology, medical science, renewable energy, Space exploration et cetera.

High level of education:-

A unique and different education system prevails having characteristics of high quality, universal accessibility, and skill-providing. literacy rates are typically very high and various opportunities for specialized training and professional development with formal education are observed.

Political stability rules of law:-

A strong, stable, educated, and experienced political system with the great extent of a democratic and rational legal framework, and great respect for human rights observed. where the rule of law is well enforced to every section equally and ensures the protection of individual freedom and human rights.

Well-developed healthcare facilities:-

In developed nations, the healthcare industry is up to the mark having advanced medical facilities with highly trained professionals. also, R&D and technology are up to the nautch which ultimately tends to high life expectancy and low infant mortality rate.

low level of inequality and poverty:-

Income and wealth distribution in such nations are quite effective, while they also have social safety nets and welfare schemes (like unemployment benefits, pensions, public housing, sanitary, and basic public amenities) to help reduce poverty.

Environmental awareness:-

Developed Nations indulge in sustainable practices with policies aspiring to reduce pollution, promote renewable energy, conserving natural resources. more in recent times (ecosystem) waste management and sustainable industrial practices to minimize environmental damage.

High life expectancy and low infant mortality:-

Due to extensive health services, sound living conditions, and appropriate nutrition intake in developed Nations, it tends to live longer with a life expectancy often exceeding 75 to 80 and a low infant mortality rate.

Strong social welfare system:-

Social security, pensions, unemployment benefits, et cetera social safety nets help to create a strong social welfare system that helps protect citizens from the negative impact of unemployment aging, or health-related issues.

Low crime rate and social stability:-

Due to effective law enforcement, better education, and high social trust very minimal social evils were observed.

Low unemployment in high labor participation:-

Due to the high output in the country, diverse employment opportunities are found. appropriate labor rights and a strong entrepreneurial ecosystem low unemployment and high labor participation were found.

High moral and ethical values:-

high moral and ethical values due to a vast understanding, ideal population, great social trust, and belief in humanity.

There are many other characteristics like international influence and geopolitical power, high corporate social responsibility, work-life balance, low population, equal opportunities, high volunteerism, sound crisis management high trust in public institutions with great extent of transparency, and many more.

V. WELFARE APPROACH

Here above-mentioned are some characteristics of the developed nation. From them growth-oriented are few but major targeting human resources in the country as observed. so it is advisable to put the weight on the development of human resources in the country, as it enhances the welfare state of the country along with getting the tag of the developed nation. Also, we know the basic problems of economics what, how, and for whom so we are well clear about what, we have to achieve the state of development. Further, how is defended by for whom as we know major characteristics of a developed nation is human resource centric and we are ultimately trying to raise the welfare of human resources so by human resources development goal of development is achievable. Below-mentioned development model emphasizes human resources to achieve the goal of getting developed.

Model of Development of Nation:

The development of a nation is a function of human development because developed human resources change the entire condition prevailing in the nation, improve it, motivate other human resources for development, and also increase the state of welfare. Hence, it is concluded that human resource development tends to nation-building. The function of Nation Development is noted below.

$$D_n = \{ H_d \},$$

Where D_n indicates the development of the nation and H_d indicates human development.

Here Human development is a function of regional development, the appropriate size of the population, and favorable environmental conditions et cetera. Human development function is noted below.

$$H_d = \{ R_d, P, E_c, Q_Ls \dots \}$$

Where R_d indicates Regional Development, P indicates the appropriate size of the Population, E_c indicates favorable Environmental conditions, and Q_Ls indicate the quality of living standard.

Here Regional Development includes factors like basic necessities (food, clothing, and shelter), and basic economic services like transportation, communication, medical facilities, education facilities, insurance, sanitation, water, electricity, etc.

Appropriate size of the population including total population and demographic allocation (how much working population, and management of component age wise and gender wise).

Favorable environmental conditions refer to ideal greenhouse gas emissions, appropriate green space, and safety for each and every ecosystem. And high living standards.

By following this model we can achieve the goal of economic and social development in the nation by increasing welfare as well as achieving growth.

Further moving, only growth and development in terms of various pre-determined scales are considered but as it is subjective we cannot judge by that particular measure whether individuals of that particular region have satiety from life or not, for example in countries like India, saint have their utility from devotion so we cannot say that they are not satisfied from their condition or not developed. as they are expert at yoga and in various traditional knowledge so here concept of life satiety index plays an important

role as it consider development by life satiety. Further unlimited wants of humans are ironic hence consideration of the life satiety index is important

Life satiety index will continued in some other paper but the point is by developing human resources we can achieve our goal of development.

VI. CONCLUSION:

As mentioned above in the model of the development of any nation, the role of human development plays a very crucial role as it further creates a positive externality. So at the ground level, we have to emphasize human development through social welfare schemes, raising education, research and development, advanced health facilities, technological innovation with environmental sustainability, likewise various other parameters, and enforcing the rule of law in each section so that we can achieve inclusive as this allows us to gain economic growth automatically. By allowing human resources to be developed it is obvious economic growth will also achieved as a byproduct here concluding $D_n = \{ H_d \}$, but it is only possible when we implement various policies and programs at ground level.

REFERENCES

1. Fooladi, S. H., Nozary, Z., & Ghatfan, F. (n.d.). Analysis of the challenges of the UN Sustainable Development Goals in developed and developing countries based on the management of economic indicators of development in health sector programs.
2. Human Development Report 2020: The next frontier - Human development and the Anthropocene - World | ReliefWeb. (2020, December 15). <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/human-development-report-2020-next-frontier-human-development-and-anthropocene>
3. Measuring the Wealth of Nations: A review. (n.d.). Measuring the Wealth of Nations.
4. OECD. (2024). How's Life? 2024: Well-being and Resilience in Times of Crisis. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/90ba854a-en>
5. OECD. (2025). Building child-friendly neighbourhoods: Empowering communities with data-driven action (33rd ed., OECD Papers on Well-Being and Inequalities) [OECD Papers on Well-being and Inequalities]. <https://doi.org/10.1787/4f46a260-en>